

**The measurement of regulator independence in practice: Latin
America and the Caribbean**

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Abstract

We present case studies of the evolution of regulatory independence in practice for 23 Latin American and Caribbean countries in the telecommunications industry. Based on these studies, we construct two realistic indices of regulatory independence, which improve upon the measures of independence that have been used so far in the empirical regulation literature. We show that legal indices may give a partially distorted picture of the commitment ability of institutions and of the impact of independence on network penetration.

Key Words: regulation, independence, strategic delegation, telecommunications.

JEL Classification Numbers: L51

1. Introduction

Institutions matter in any field of economic policy. For example, the econometric treatment of the effects of good institutions on macroeconomic performance is a very active field of research, and is increasingly inspiring empirical research in microeconomic policies. Credible commitments are seen as one of the few recommendations that survive after many studies, although the recommendation leaves broad space to fill in the details. Levy and Spiller (1996) stress this point for the case of the regulation of privatized utilities.

The analysis of the independence of regulatory agencies is part of this increasing interest on the institutions of economic policy. Independence is seen in the economics literature as a way to strategically delegate into an agent (the regulator) who is more reluctant than a representative government to expropriate specific investments. An independent regulatory agency is also seen as a way to attract professional experts and to stabilize policies in the presence of political volatility (see Evans et al., 2007).

Even do the telecommunications sector, given that among all the utility sectors it is the one less prone to regulatory opportunism, given that assets are not as long lived. Work on the measurement of Telecommunications Regulatory Agencies (TRA) independence has tended to analyze legal or *de jure* independence but not independence in practice or *de facto* independence. Most, but not all, of the work on legal independence, has used dichotomous dummy variables, and these, as Estache et al. (2006, 12) point out, “may not capture the degree of independence”. Others use indices reporting about the legal framework: whether there is primary legislation requiring an independent regulator, how is it funded, to whom should he or she report, etc.¹. By independence in practice or *de facto* independence we mean what actually happens en la relación *real* de las instituciones con el resto del gobierno, and which could be measured (at least in part).

In this paper, we report a first attempt to measure independence in practice (for telecommunications regulators in Latin America and the Caribbean), by undertaking case studies which show regulators’ turnover ratio and allow us to quantify their vulnerability. The empirical methodology draws from the literature on Central Bank Independence. In the rest of this paper, in Section 2 we present some background on the independence debate and regulatory reform in Latin America. In Section 3 we present case studies on 23 countries and build on these to construct indices of independence in practice. In Section 4 we present some basic, illustrative econometrics to put our measures to work. And finally we conclude in Section 5.

¹ Stern and Cubbin (2003), Pargal (2003), Edwards and Wavermann (2006), Gual and Trillas (2004 and 2006) and Montoya and Trillas (2007) are representative of this line of research and acknowledge the need for indices of independence in practice. See also Gutierrez (2003a), Ros (1999 and 2003), Viani (2006), Wallsten (2003), Ai et al. (2004) and Fink et al. (2002).

2. Background

The independence issue and the research agenda in regulation and monetary policy

In infrastructure industries, the importance of institutions is mainly driven by the sunk nature of the investments needed, which is the source of a time inconsistency problem, highlighted by Levy and Spiller (1996), Shirley et al. (2000), Noll (2000), Noll and Shirley (2002), Gutiérrez (2003a), Levine et al. (2005) and Newbery (2000), among others. Many countries face major difficulties in inducing sufficient investment to meet demand at an acceptable cost. Hence, the role of the regulatory institutions is crucial in providing the credibility that will support the necessary investment flows. Falta completar más del hold up problem.

The following picture of an extensive form game summarizes with the simplest of models the time inconsistency problem in regulation that gives rise to the “independence” solution:

In the game described in the picture, first a firm makes a decision on whether to undertake a specific investment (for example, a fibre optic network) or not, and next the regulator, if the firm has invested, decides whether to fix a price that remunerates the investment, or to expropriate this investment (zero price). The payoff of the firm is $P-I$, whereas the payoff of the (consumer welfare maximizing) regulator is $2I-P$. By backwards induction, if the firm has invested ($I=1$), the regulator will rationally fix $P=0$, and, anticipating this, the firm will not invest ($I=0$). Hence, in a subgame perfect equilibrium, there is no investment. More realistic settings would include many other real world details, but if there is no commitment and assets are sunk, underinvestment would remain a serious concern, perhaps in the form of bad maintenance or use of inefficient technologies.

The expropriation of the quasi-rents derived from specific investment may not necessarily take the form of too low prices (revisar), but it can take other forms, such as

unexpected investment requirements, costly unanticipated quality improvements, or requirements to hire inefficient staff. Policy makers may follow this path and still benefit from the (already in place) investments. Ex ante, however, investors will anticipate this, and investment levels will be sub-optimal. The opportunity cost of renegeing will depend on country characteristics, such as the institutional endowment, the degree of income inequality, or the nature of fiscal systems. In countries with skewed income distributions, governments pay a political price in terms of not satisfying the median (relatively poor) voter if they do not renege on promises made to remunerate specific investments. The problem may be alleviated by long term contracts, repeated interactions, reputational mechanisms or institutions that make credible that the $P=0$ path will not be taken. Historically, public ownership (the state internalizing the firm's problem) has been a way to alleviate time inconsistency, but in the recent decades policy makers in many countries recognized that the costs of public ownership in terms of public funds and inefficient practices outweighed its benefits. Thus, the solution of privatizing and strategically delegating into an independent regulator, in a similar way as governments delegate into an inflation-averse central banker (see Levine et al., 2005). The need for experts in technologically complex sectors and the wish to give certainty in politically volatile regions reinforce the argument of independence.

However, it is not axiomatic that independence will automatically yield good investment results, as there are other mechanisms to achieve commitment, to attract experts, and to avoid political volatility (revisar). For example, it is widely recognized that Chile has achieved a high degree of commitment in privatizing utilities through a very detailed and difficult to change legislation. It is an empirical question whether Chile is an exception that can be explained by a very specific political and institutional system that makes policy reversal very difficult, or whether it is an example that can be generalized.

One problem of course is that independence does not solve, but it relocates, the commitment problem, which transforms itself into one of the government credibly committing not to undermine the independence of the regulator, which many countries have found very difficult, as we show below in Section 3. Then a potential measure of independence in practice is for how long do politicians respect the period in office of appointed regulators. And this is the research strategy we follow below.

The measurement of independence in practice for Central Banks is quite developed in the literature.² In a definition of Central Bank independence, Walsh (2005, 10) states that "legal measures of Central Bank independence may not reflect the relationship between the Central Bank and the government that actually exist in practice." Hence, it is important to develop indices of independence in practice. Commitment is actually more difficult to achieve in regulation than in monetary policy, given that slow asset depreciation and slow demand growth increase the length of the period during which governments have the temptation to renege on previous regulatory promises (see Levine et al., 2005).³

² See Eijffinger and De Haan (1996), De Haan and Kooi (2000) and Arnone, Laurens and Segalotto (2006).

³ Another difference with monetary policy is that the task of central bankers is more predictable and focused than the multi-dimensional job of a regulator.

As a *proxy* for independence in practice Cukierman (1992) uses the average time (or turnover ratio) in the position of Central Bank governor or chairman. As an example of the empirical literature on Central Bank independence, Cukierman clarifies that there is no obvious measure of actual (in practice) independence as opposed to legal Central Bank independence. He points out that this is not because it is not important, but “because it is difficult to find a group of systematic measures of actual independence when this diverges from legal independence” (383). He finds that the measure of legal independence and the turnover rate of the Central Bank governor differ by a larger amount in developing rather than in developed countries.

A independent regulator is generally associated with attempts to reform regulation. Wallsten (2001, 8) argues that having a separate regulator is a sign of how willing a country is to reform regulation. There are at least ten studies about telecommunications regulation which measure legal (*de jure*) independence of the regulatory agency; five of them use dichotomous variables and the others use indices, but none of them measures independence in practice. In most (but not all) cases the measures that have been used so far have a positive impact on some performance measures (typically, network penetration, see Table 1).

Table 1. Studies on Telecommunications Regulation and Telecommunications Regulatory Authorities (TRAs)

<i>Study</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Characteristics</i>	<i>Data Sources</i>	<i>Result</i>
Bortolotti et al. (2002)	<i>D</i>	Date in which the agency starts operating	ITU	The creation of TRA is non-significant in most estimations
Edwards and Waverman (2005)	<i>I</i>	Twelve-component index	EC and other	TRA' independence is significant by itself and interacting with privatization
Fink et al. (2002)	<i>D</i>	Whether country has a separate regulatory agency or otherwise	ITU	Significant in most estimations
Gual and Trillas (2004)	<i>I</i>	Nine-component index	ITU, OECD, and others	Legal TRA is non-significant.
Gutiérrez (2003a)	<i>I</i>	Four-dimension index of regulatory governance	Own research	Positive and significant (at 1% level) in tele-density and efficiency (at 10% level)

Henisz et al. (2005)	<i>I</i>	Four dimension index	ITU	Deregulation is robust and significant
Pargal (2003)	<i>I</i>	Six-dimension index	Guasch (2001)	TRA independence gives mixed results depending on the dimension
Ros (2003)	<i>D</i>	Whether there is a separate agency	ITU	Positive and significant at 10% level for expansion and at 1% level for efficiency.
Wallsten (2001)	<i>D</i>	Whether the country's agency is under the control of a Ministry.	ITU	Non-significant at 1% and not always at 5%
Wallsten (2003)	<i>D</i>	Whether the agency was established before privatization.	ITU	Positive and significant in three different regressions.
	<i>D</i>	Whether the Regulatory agency states that it is independent relative to politicians.	ITU	Negative and significant at 5%

D: Dummy; *I*: Index

The literature points out that it is difficult⁴, for developing countries, to find credible (and consistent over time) alternatives to an independent regulatory agency.

Edwards and Waverman (2005, 25) argue, independence is more than a group of formal institutional rules; it also has important informal aspect which usually depends on centuries of legal and political traditions, cultural norms and individuals.

We therefore think that more emphasis should be put on *de facto* regulatory independence. Edwards and Waverman (2005) suggest that there seems to be a negative correlation between formal (*de jure*) regulatory independence and independence in practice (*de facto*), because in those countries with weak informal mechanisms to ensure Regulatory independence, these are compensated with strong formal arrangements in order to persuade potential investors that there is no regulatory bias.⁵

The drawback of legal indices or dichotomous variables which measure Regulatory independence is that they only reflect the state of legislation and events and politicians may leave the law aside.⁶ An implication of this is that inferences derived

⁴ See Gutierrez (2003a) and Levine et al. (2005)

⁵ However, they do not measure empirically the practice of independence in their work.

⁶ An illustrative example of the problems of appointment, continuity and independence of commissioners in a regulatory agency is the regulation of electricity in India, where laws establish that commissioners' appointments must be for 5 years with a compulsory retirement age of 62. Most commissioners are

from such data sets for telecommunications, electricity and other industries can give distorted pictures about the real effect of regulatory governance, as Stern and Cubbin (2003, 22) point out.

Thus there is the need to enlarge the data bases to develop empirical work which test the effects of a well functioning regulatory regime using data about the process or practice of regulation, for example, as stated by Levine, et al. (2005, 469), by measuring “the percentage of commissioners or directors of regulatory agencies who end their term prematurely.” The empirical evidence on the effectiveness of Central Bank Independence support this notion. Pargal (2003) also points out, when explaining the limitations of his research, that lack of data made impossible to assess the importance of aspects of independence such as security and duration of the contract of the regulator.⁷

2.2. Regulatory Reform in Latin America and the Caribbean

Since the 1990s institutional reforms began in many countries, especially in Latin America. Many started by opening up infrastructure public monopolies to private investment. Some followed by a reluctant introduction of competition. Liberalization was accompanied by government regulation, be it through direct ministerial regulation or through a separate regulatory agency.⁸

In the infrastructure sectors, private investment has increased the most in the telecommunications sector, and the Latin America and Caribbean region is the one that most private resources has attracted, with a peak in 1997.⁹ In the subsequent years, however, private investment declined, reflecting according to some (see Easterly and Serven, 2003) the difficulties of creating regulatory safeguards to specific private quasi-rents in a context of acute social problems in increasingly democratic societies. This has coincided with major technological changes in telecommunications, eliminating the natural monopoly in many segments. Of the 23 Telecommunications Regulatory Authorities (TRAs) analyzed in this paper, 17 were created between 1977 and 1996; the remaining 6 since 1997.

Para ilustrar lo anterior, Table 2 shows four groups of indicators and indices for 23 countries of Latin America and the Caribbean: (i) Economic, (ii) Political, and (iii) Telecommunications performance. They are for the period 1990-2004 and for a subdivision of the period (1990-1996 and 1997-2004).

En la dimensión macroeconómica de las políticas encontramos que los Economic indicators show that growth of income in the region has been moderate, being the figures for the second half of the period better than the first. The degree of trade openness has almost not varied for the 15 years of the sample.

appointed around 60 years old, so that they can only stay in their jobs for 2 or 3 years, according to Stern and Cubbin (2003, 18).

⁷ See also Wallsten (2003) or Estache et al. (2006).

⁸ Some of the studies that analyze the process of institutional reforms are Gómez-Ibañez (2003), Eastely and Serven (2003), Kessides (2004), and Laffont (2005).

⁹ See Harris (2003).

Concerning economic indices, the Economic Freedom Index and the Overall Regulation of the Fraser Institute, show a region that is open to free enterprise, especially in the second period, and which shows an improving regulation of credit, work and businesses.^{10 11}

En la literatura de la independencia del Banco Central se señala que el proceso y los cambios políticos pueden estar relacionados con los cambios en las instituciones¹². Para América Latina, political indicators in the region show a consolidation and normalization of democracy in the region. The tenure of presidents or prime ministers becomes longer, the average age of democracy increases, reaching 25 years for the period 1997-2004, and the Herfindahl Index of the Legislature remains stable.^{13 14} The variable Political Constraints (PolCon III), measuring the probability of policy reversals, also stays unchanged.^{15 16} As it is well known, the legal origin of the region is mostly French.^{17 18}

Telecommunications data show an expanding sector, with strong network growth as measured by telephone lines per 100 inhabitants, and also a more productive sector, as the staff that works in the sector as a percentage of the population has diminished.^{19 20}

¹⁰ The Fraser Institute creates, for 129 countries in the period 1970-2004, the data base about “Economic Freedom in the World”, with 29 variables, related to i) government size; ii) legal structure and safety of property rights; iii) access to safe money; iv) freedom of trade; v) regulation of credit, work and businesses. See Gwartney y Lawson (2005) and <http://www.freetheworld.com/>

¹¹ These indices have been used for the study of telecommunications by Gutiérrez (2003b).

¹² See Cukierman (1992), Cukierman and Webb (1995) and De Haan y Kooi (2000)

¹³ These data come from the “Political Institutions Data Base” of the World Bank. See Beck et al. (2001) and http://www.worldbank.org/wbi/governance/other_data.html

¹⁴ For the study of telecommunications, this data base has been used by Li and Xu (2002) and Gual and Trillas (2004 and 2006).

¹⁵ The data base on “policy constraints” due to Henisz (2000) is based on four variables that help estimate the probability of policy reversal for the period between 1900 and 2004, for 234 countries.

¹⁶ For the study of the privatization, liberalization and regulation of telecommunications, it has been used by Henisz and Zeller (2001), Gual and Trillas (2004) and mentioned by Gutiérrez (2003b) and Jamison et al.(2005). Henisz, et al. (2005) create and use a data base with three variables to measure (formal) regulator independence, competition and privatization for 205 countries in the period 1960-1999. Both data bases can be obtained in <http://www-management.wharton.upenn.edu/henisz/>

¹⁷ The data base reported in La Porta et.al (2002) informs about the legal origin of countries’ institutional systems.

¹⁸ In the study of telecommunications Gual and Trillas (2004) have used this data base. La Porta has also participated in the construction of a data base containing 20 variables about governance, institutions and social issues for 135 countries between 1960 and 2000 in Glaeser et al. (2004). These data have not been used in the study of telecommunications, to our knowledge. Both data bases can be found in <http://mba.tuck.dartmouth.edu/pages/faculty/rafael.laporta/publications.html>

¹⁹ The International Telecommunications Union (ITU) publishes its own data base with 83 performance variables for 150 countries. See <http://www.itu.int/home/index.html>.

²⁰ The efficiency data have been used by Ros (2003), Gual and Trillas (2004 and 2006) and by Gutierrez (2003a).

Table 2. Economic, political, and telecom data for 23 Latin America and the Caribbean countries.

Period	1990-2004	1990-1996	1997-2004
<i>Economic & Country Indicators</i>			
GDP per capita (2000 US\$)	3325	3125	3500
Annual growth rate of GDP per capita (%)	1.10	0.69	3.34
GDP per capita ppp (2000 international \$)	6155	5815	6454
Trade (exports plus imports as % of GDP)	32	31	32
Economic Freedom Index	6.09	5.72	6.41
Overall Regulation	5.73	5.57	5.87
Density (people per sq-kilometer)	82	78	86
<i>Political Indices</i>			
Years President	3.4	3.1	3.6
Democratic Age	21	17	25
Herfindahl Index	0.38	0.37	0.38
PolCon III	0.39	0.38	0.39
Legal Origen	0.8	0.8	0.8
<i>Telecommunications indicators</i>			
Main lines per 100 inhabitants	12.31	9.17	15.06
Full time telecom staff (per '000 inhab)	1.23	1.27	1.19

Source: World Bank Development Indicators, Economic Freedom Index Gwartney & Lawson (2005), Database of Political Institutions. Beck et al (2001), Henisz et al (2005), La Porta et al (2002), ITU World Telecommunication Database. Note: The countries in the sample are Argentina, Barbados, Belize, Bolivia, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, Dominican R., Ecuador, Salvador, Guatemala, Honduras, Jamaica, México, Nicaragua, Panama, Paraguay, Peru, Surinam, Trinidad and Tobago, Uruguay and Venezuela.

3. The Construction of Measures of Independent Regulation in Practice

In this Section, we first explain the data collection process about the beginning and end of the period in office of the head of TRA (Telecommunications Regulatory Authority). Next we explain the construction of a vulnerability index which uses the

changes in the head of the agency as a measure of independence in practice. Después se explica la construcción del Índice de Independencia en la Práctica que recoge y pondera el motivo por el cual el director deja el cargo. Con la combinación de cada uno de estos índices de independencia (en la práctica) con un índice de independencia legal se crean dos índices de independencia legal y en la práctica para 23 países de América Latina y el Caribe.

Data collection

To create a vulnerability index and a practical independence index in Latin American TRA it is key to have information about the exact date of beginning and end of the period in office of the head of the agency as well la razón por la que el director se retira del cargo (fin de periodo, despido u otro).²¹

We obtained complete data on the beginning and end of the director or chair person of the agency for 23 countries in the Latin America and Caribbean region for the period between 1990 and 2004.²² Más investigación de campo es requerida para obtener algunas fechas exactas.

Therefore, to obtain the necessary data we resorted mainly to three groups of sources:

- i) The TRA's themselves. In some cases, in their web pages there are press bulletins, decrees, contracts, speeches or notes about the beginning and/or end of the time in office of the head.²³
- ii) Data bases of news about the region, such as *ISI Emerging Markets*, *ProQuest* and *Lexis-Nexis*. We also used the press of every country as well as contact with some analysts or local telecommunications research centres.²⁴
- iii) Bulletins and web pages of the above mentioned organizations AHCIET, ITU and REGULATEL.²⁵

²¹ Se considera que el director de la agencia es el miembro más importante de la institución, sin embargo existen ejemplos, como Colombia, donde el gobierno de la agencia esta en manos de un consejo donde cada miembro tiene el mismo peso. Incluso la presidencia es rotativa entre sus miembros (cada 16 meses).

²² For Haiti and Guyana it was impossible to obtain complete data for the period. We also exclude Cuba and Puerto Rico for their specific political or market characteristics.

²³ For an analysis comparing the web sites of TRA in Latin America and the Caribbean, see Mahan (2005).

²⁴ In the case of Mexico, for example, we contacted the *Instituto del Derecho de las Telecomunicaciones* (IDET), the *Programa de Investigación de las Telecomunicaciones* from *Centro de Investigación y Docencia Económica* (CIDE) and a specialised editorialist in newspaper *Reforma*.

²⁵ Their web pages are: <http://www.ahciet.net> (AHCIET), <http://www.itu.int> (ITU), <http://www.regulatel.org> (REGULATEL).

Table 3. Telecom regulation agency and their presidents. 1990-2004

Country	Name of de Agency	Year of creation	President/Director Name	Start	End	Months
Argentina	Comisión Nacional De Telecomunicaciones	1990	Ceferino Namuncura	Jun-04	---	---
			Falvio M. Madaro	Jun-03	Jun-04	13
			Adolfo Luis Italiano	Mar-02	Jun-03	15
			Carlos Forno	Dec-99	Mar-02	27
			Roberto Catalan	Feb-97	Dec-99	35
			Alberto Gabrielli	Mar-96	Feb-97	11
			Raúl Agüero	May-95	Mar-96	10
			Oscar Gonzalez	Jun-94	May-95	11
			Rinaldo Colomé	Oct-93	Jun-94	8
			José L. Palazzo	Nov-91	Oct-93	23
			Raúl Otero	Jan-90	Nov-91 ^a	22
Barbados	Fair Trading Commission	2001 ^b	Neville Nicholls	Dec-03	---	---
			Frank King	Jan-01	Dec-03	35
Belice	Public Utilities Commission	1999	Gilbert Canton	Jan-99	---	---
Bolivia	Superintendencia de Telecomunicaciones	1995	René Bustillo P.	Jan-03	---	---
			Guido Loayza M.	Dec-97	Jan-03	61
			Carlos Saravia D.	Nov-95	Dec-97	25
Brazil	Agência Nacional de Telecomunicações	1997	Pedro J. Ziller de A.	Jan-04	---	---
			Luiz G. Schymura de O.	May-02	Jan-04	20
			Antônio C. Valente da S.	Mar-02	May-02	1
			Renato Navarro G.	Nov-97	Mar-02	53
Chile	Subsecretaria de Telecomunicaciones	1977	Chistian Nicolai O.	Mar-00	---	---
			Juanita Gana	Aug-97	Mar-00	31
			Gregorio San Martín	Mar-94	Aug-97	41
			Roberto Pliscoff	Mar-90 ^c	Mar-94 ^d	48
Colombia	Comisión de Regulación de las Telecomunicaciones	1994	Gabriel A. Jurado	Sep-04	---	---
			Mauricio López C.	May-03	Aug-04	16
			Carlos E. Balen y V.	Sep-01	Apr-03	20
			Néstor Roa B.	Aug-00	Aug-01	13
			Diego Molano V.	Sep-98	Jul-00	23
			Gustavo Peña Q.	Dec-97	Aug-98	8
			Douglas Velásquez J.	Nov-96	Dec-97	13
			Hilda M. Pardo H.	Feb-96	Oct-96	8
			Daniel E. Medina V.	Oct-94	Feb-96	16
Costa Rica	Autoridad Reguladora de los Servicios Públicos	1996	María J. París	Jan-94	Oct-94	9
			Aracelly Pacheco S.	Sep-03	---	---
			Hermann Hess A.	May-02	Aug-03	16
			Leonel Fonseca C.	Jun-98	May-02	46
			Rafael Carrillo L.	Aug-97	May-98	9
Dominican R.	Instituto Dominicano de las Telecomunicaciones	1998	Leonel Fonseca C.	Oct-96	Aug-97	10
			José R. Vargas	Aug-04	---	---
			Orlando J. Mera	Aug-00	Aug-04	48
			Mariano G. Mejía	Jul-00	Aug-00	1
Ecuador	Consejo Nacional de Telecomunicaciones	1995	José G. Sued	Apr-99 ^e	Jul-00	16
			Freddy Rodríguez F.	Jan-03	---	---
			José Pileggi V.	Feb-00	Jan-03	35
			Juan Hidalgo G.	Feb-99	Jan-00	10
			Mario Burbano De L.	Mar-97	Aug-98	17
Carlos Manzur P.	Aug-96	Feb-97	6			

El Salvador	Superintendencia General de Electricidad y Telecomunicaciones	1996	Esteban Pólit M.	Jan-96 ^f	Aug-96	8
			Jorge I. Nieto M.	Jun-04	---	---
			José L. Trigueros.	Sep-01	May-04	33
			Ernesto Lima M.	Jul-99	Aug-01	25
			Erick Casamiquela	Dec-97	Jul-99	17
Guatemala	Superintendencia de Telecomunicaciones	1996	Orlando de Sola	Sep-96	Aug-97	15
			Oscar Chinchilla G.	Jan-04	---	---
			José Orellana M.	Jan-00	Jan-04 ^g	48
			José Toledo O.	Feb-99	Jan-00 ^h	11
			Mario Roberto P.	Sep-98	Feb-99 ⁱ	6
Honduras	Comisión Nacional de Telecomunicaciones	1995	José Toledo O.	Nov-96	Sep-98 ^j	22
			David A. Matamoros B.	Jan-04 ^k	---	---
			Marlon Ramssés T.	Nov-02	Dec-03	13
			Norman Roy H.	Mar-98	Oct-02	55
			Adolfo L. Sevilla G.	Mar-98	Mar-98	0
Jamaica	Office of Utilities Regulation	1995	Francisco J. Valenzuela	Jul-96	Dec-97	17
			José G. Aquino	Oct-95	Jun-96	8
			J. Paul Morgan	Feb-03	---	---
			Winston Hay	Apr-95	Jan-03 ^l	94
			Jorge Arredondo M.	Nov-01	---	---
Mexico	Comisión Federal de Telecomunicaciones	1996	Jorge Nicolin F.	Jun-99	Nov-01	29
			Javier Lozano	Apr-98	May-99	13
			Carlos Casassus	Aug-96	Apr-98	21
			Joel Gutiérrez	Jun-04	---	---
			Eduardo Urcuyo L.	Dec-03	Jun-04	6
Nicaragua	Instituto Nicaragüense de Telecomunicaciones y Correos	1995	Fausto Carcabelos	Aug-03	Dec-03	3
			Mario Gonzalez L.	Jan-02	Aug-03	19
			David Robleto	Feb-01	Jan-02	11
			Mario Gonzalez L.	Sep-99	Feb-01	28
			Mario Montenegro	Jan-97	Sep-99	49
Panama	Ente Regulador de Servicios Públicos	1996	Rolando Rivas H.	Aug-95	Jan-97 ^m	49
			José Galán P.	Oct-04	---	---
			José D. Palermo	Dec-03	Oct-04	10
			Alex A. Arroyo M.	Feb-00	Dec-03	46
			José Guanti G.	Aug-96 ⁿ	Feb-00	43
Paraguay	Comisión Nacional de Telecomunicaciones	1995	Luis A. Reinoso Z.	Jul-04	---	---
			Omar J. Ramos L.	Aug-03	Jul-04	11
			Oswaldo Bergonzi	Jan-03	Aug-03	7
			Victor A. Bogado G.	Jan-00	Jan-03	36
			Juan M. Cano F.	Jul-96 ^o	Dec-99	42
Peru	Organismo Supervisor de Inversión Privada en Telecomunicaciones	1994	Edwin San Román Z.	Feb-02	---	---
			Jorge Kunigami K.	Jan-94 ^p	Jan-02	95
Suriname	Telecommunicatie Autoriteit Suriname	1998	H.Guno Cautelen	Aug-00	---	---
			Dick De Bie	Jan-98 ^q	Aug-00	31
Trinidad & Tobago	Telecommunications Authority of Trinidad and Tobago	2002 ^r	Ralph Henry	Aug-04	---	---
Uruguay	Unidad Reguladora de Servicios de Comunicaciones	2001	David Soverall	Jan-02	Jul-04	30
			Fernando Pérez Tabó	Feb-01	---	---
Venezuela	Consejo Nacional de las Telecomunicaciones	1991	Alvin R. Lezama P.	Jul-03	---	---
			Jesse Chacon	May-01	Jul-03	26
			Diosdado Cabello	Feb-99	May-01	27
			José M. Padron I.	Jul-98	Feb-99	6
			José L. Avilez N.	Aug-96	Jul-98	24
			José Soriano	Oct-91	Aug-96	58
			Juan Mijares	Sep-91	Oct-91	1

Source: TRA's web pages, press bulletins, decrees, contracts and notes; ISI Emerging Markets, ProQuest, Lexis-Nexis, local press; bulletins and web pages of AHCJET, ITU and REGULATEL.

Notes:

- a. We did not find the exact dates of the departure of Raul Otero and the arrival of José L. Palazzo, so we approximated the dates following notes on activities of both in newspaper "El Cronista" from Buenos Aires.
- b. From 1978 to 2000 Public Utilities Board was operating. FTC was established as a statutory corporation on January 2nd, 2001 by the Fair Trading Commission Act 2001-31.
- c. It has been followed since 1990.
- d. We did not find the exact dates of the departure of Roberto Pliscoff and the arrival of Gregorio San Martin, but since the deputy secretary is appointed by the new country's president we assume that turnover coincides with the replacement of Aylwin by Frei (March 1994). This coincides with notes on activities of both regulator according to newspaper El Mercurio from Santiago.
- e. Although the Regulatory body is created on May 27th, the board was appointed by presidential decree until April 1999.
- f. Although it is created on August 30th 1995, the first president of CONATEL starts his tenure on this date.
- g. We did not find the exact dates, so we approximated according to the Fac. That the Superintendent is appointed by the new Ministry of Communications and Infrastructure. We assumed that the turnover coincided with the change from Portillo to Berger in the country (January 1994). We also revised the public signed documents in the web page of SIT; the last document signed by José Orellana i son December 2003 and the first signed by Oscar Chinchilla is on May 2004.
- h. We did not find the exact dates, and assumed that the turnover coincided with the change from Arzú to Portillo in the country (January 2000). We also revised the signed documents published in the web page of SIT. The last document signed by José Toledo is from December 1999 and the first signed by José Orellana is from April 2000.
- i. We did not find the exact dates, so we approximated following signed documents published in the web page of SIT. The last document signed by Mario Paz is from January 1999 and the first signed by José Toledo is from April 1999.
- j. We did not find the exact dates, so we approximated based on signed documents Publisher in the web page of SIT. The last document signed by José Toledo is from August 1998 and the first one signed by Mario Paz is from October 1998.
- k. We did not find the exact dates, so that we approximated following signed resolutions Publisher in the web page of CONATEL. The first resolution signed by David Matamoros is from January 2004.
- l. We did not find the exact dates, so we approximated following speeches available on the web page of OUR. The last speech by Winston Hay was on January 2003 and the first speech by Paul Morgan was on March 2003.
- m. We did not find the exact dates of the departure of Rolando Rivas and the arrival of Mario Montenegro. We approximated following notes on the activities of both in newspaper "El Nuevo Diario" from and a note on *Nicaragua Country Commercial Guide 1996* from the *U.S. Department of State*.
- n. It is created on January 29th 1996 but it starts functioning in August.
- o. The law creating it is from May 25th 1995 but it starts functioning on July 1996.
- p. There are laws from 1991 and 1993. But it starts functioning on 1994.
- q. Since 1980 the Ministry of Transportation, Communications and Tourism was responsible for Telecommunications.
- r. Trinidad and Tobago's Telecommunications Authority (TTTEL) was created in 2002. Following the promulgation of the Telecommunications (Amendment) Act 2004, the TATT was established replacing TTTEL.

Of the 17 countries which have a period established by law in the region, only in four of them the regulator completes the full period: Belize, Jamaica, Uruguay and Peru (which actually goes beyond the prescribed period), and the remainder (with the exception of Bolivia, Colombia and Surinam), stay in approximately half of the prescribed period.²⁶

There is no precedent in the literature for measuring the independence in practice of TRA's. Drawing from the studies on Central Bank independence, we

²⁶ Those countries are: Argentina, Barbados, Belice, Bolivia, Brasil, Colombia, Costa Rica, Dominican R., Ecuador, El Salvador, Honduras, Jamaica, Paraguay, Peru, Surinam, Trinidad and Tobago and Uruguay. The average of legally prescribed is 54 months.

construct two variables that tries to reflect the independence in practice through (i) the index of political vulnerability, that is, the number of months that elapse between a change in the country's executive power and a change in the head/director of the agency, and (ii) the practical independence index que mide el motivo por el que el head/director de la agencia deja el cargo.

Political Vulnerability Index

As mentioned in the first section, Cukierman and Webb (1995) present an index of political vulnerability for Central Bank governors for countries all over the world. They argue that computing the turnover rate of the governor relative to political changes is important to evaluate the size and effect of these in the frequency of regulatory turnover. They think of this index as a measure of political influence. Thus, the formula of the index of (inverse) political vulnerability of TRA is defined for each country as the fraction of political transitions (presidential/prime minister transition only) that are not quickly followed by a replacement in the director/chair of agency:

$$V(i) \equiv \frac{\text{Number of regulators that stay in his or her position for } i \text{ months after a political transition}}{\text{Number of political transitions}}, i = 1, \dots, n$$

Cukierman and Webb (1995) use in the numerator the number of political replacements, whereas we use the number of regulators that stay in his or her position for i months after a political transition. The reason for the change is that we want to give a higher score to less political influence in TRA. When measuring turnover in the head of TRA's in Latin America, we find that in 61% of occasions there is a change in the head of the agency within 1 month. If we take six months, in 73% of times in which there is a change in president there is turnover in the head of the TRA. If we take one year, the ratio rises to 88%.

With the above mentioned information about turnover in TRA's, we have chosen one month after a political change in the country as period of analysis for our sample.^{27 28}

Among the weaknesses of the index of inverse vulnerability for TRA's, one is that it does not take into account those changes in the regulator during the remainder of the presidential period and which have a political motivation, be it because it took place after 1 month since the political transition, or because there has been more than one change of regulator during one president's period. In some of these cases, they are forced resignations for political motives or rivalries which do not involve a change in

²⁷ Se elige un mes ya que el 61% de los cambios de regulador de dan 30 días después del cambio de Presidente/Primer Ministro. Las correlación entre la medida de vulnerabilidad a uno, seis y doce meses es alta.

²⁸ Barbados, Brazil and Jamaica are the only Latin American and Caribbean countries where the new country's president kept the same director at least for one year after taking office. In Dominican Republic, Ecuador, El Salvador and Guatemala when the president takes office, by law, the president must choose a new agency's head.

the executive.²⁹ There are also changes in the regulator due to cabinet reshuffles, promotions or resignations to run for elected jobs.³⁰ There are also interesting cases of directors who resign to find a job in the firms that they previously regulated, what is known in the literature as “revolving doors phenomenon”.³¹ These changes are not reflected in the index of inverse vulnerability, but a turnover rate or the frequency of changes would capture them. Other failure of the measure to take into account other forms of de facto influence of governments on regulators apart from removal of the agency head

Another situation that is not measured in the vulnerability index are those cases where the head of the agency is a member of the Executive (vulnerability 0.00) but where the period in office is longer than the region’s average, especially in countries with high stability in their cabinets and presidential periods.³²

Practical Independence Index

Junto con la información de fechas de inicio y fin real del director de las TRA también se obtuvo el motivo público por el que este deja el cargo. El índice de independencia en la práctica (PI) utiliza dicha información. Se cálculo de la siguiente manera: Se da un valor de 0 a la destitución o despido; de 1 a cualquier otro motivo de separación, excepto finalización de periodo establecido (cambio de gobierno, cambio en el gabinete, desaparición de la agencia); y de 2 cuando se finaliza en el periodo establecido.

Este índice no interactúa con los cambios en la presidencia del país pero si permite valorar los la independencia en la práctica del regulador con respecto a los motivos de su rotación en el cargo.

The Index of Independence in Law and in Practice (LPI1 and LPI2)

²⁹ One of the most representative cases is Argentina, where there have been 11 directors of regulatory agency CNC (previously CNT) in our period, and we only counted three for the index. Only in the presidency of Carlos Menem there were 7 different directors. The local press also reflects other cases of political pressures to force the resignation of the director, like in Bolivia, Brazil and Panama; or resignations due to differences amongst cabinet ministers, like in Chile; or resignations due to a change in party membership of the head of the agency, like in Nicaragua.

³⁰ We find examples in Mexico, where a director became cabinet minister; in Nicaragua and Venezuela two regulators became ministers. In Paraguay one agency head resigned to run for Parliament elections.

³¹ In Nicaragua a Director General became executive of the country’s subsidiary of the Spanish electricity firm Unión FENOSA. In Panama a former regulator founded and chaired a local and long distance telecommunications firm; in Colombia a former commissioner founded a consulting firm working for a cellular telephony firm; in Paraguay the government appointed the president of the agency as director general of the state-owned telecommunications monopoly. For an analysis of the revolving door phenomenon, see for example Che (1995) and Salant (1995).

³² Chile is the clearest of these cases. It has a low inverse vulnerability index, but the period in office of the telecommunications deputy secretary (the non-independent regulator, actually a cabinet minister) is longer than the region’s average. For our period, in this country there has been only one regulator that has not finished his period with the country’s president.

The vulnerability index has a limitation when it comes to its use in statistical analysis: it is an average figure for all the studied period, so that it only takes one value for the fifteen years of the period. This limitation causes poor estimation results. In order to overcome this limitation, we have created an Index of Independence in Law and in Practice (LPI1), which combines the time-varying Index of Regulatory Independence (IRI) shown in Montoya and Trillas (2007)³³ and the index of inverse vulnerability, through the combination of both indices ponderados al 50% cada uno. As a result, the LPI is an index that varies over time and that captures the independence in law and in practice, being the first index of this type in the literature. It takes into account the same information as IR1 (or indices that are shown in Montoya and Trillas, 2007, to be highly correlated with this, such as the one presented in Gutiérrez, 2003a), and it adds for the first time information about the degree of independence in practice relative to the political majorities.

We also have created an Index of Independence in Law and in Practice (LPI2), which combines the time-varying Index of Regulatory Independence (IR1) and the practical independence index, through the combination of both indices. As a result, the LPI2 is an index that captures the independence in law and in practice, tomando en cuenta el motivo por el que el Director de la TRA abandona el cargo.

Ranking

Concerning the relative position of the 23 countries (see Table 4), algunos países que ocupan los primeros puestos en el índice legal (IR1) también lo hacen en los índices legales y en la práctica (LPI1 y LPI2), como Peru, Bolivia y Argentina (éste último, a pesar de su pobre desempeño en la práctica es debido a su correcto aspecto legal).

In general, the countries occupying the first places at LPI1 and LPI2 can be explained by a correct legal framework, and the longevity of some of their directors, together with the fact that turnover takes places long after political change y/o el director no es despedido.³⁴

The ten lowest positions are occupied by countries characterized by agencies that are part of a Ministry, and hence with little legal independence and hence independence in practice is meaningless (Chile and Surinam); or by rules prescribing that new governments must appoint regulators (Dominican Republic and Guatemala); or by a high politicization in the appointment of the head of the agency so that turnover is frequent (Nicaragua).

Con respecto a cambios señalados en la clasificación de los países entre la medida legal y la medida combinada con la práctica, encontramos a El Salvador que tiene un correcto marco legal pero una baja independencia *de facto*, lo que hace que aparezca en

³³ IRI has 10 components which measure legal independence, it measures: (i) Years of effective operation of the agency since its legal creation. (ii) Percentage of private ownership of the incumbent. (iii) Degree to which the regulatory agency has powers in the allocation of fixed telephony licences. Powers to (iv) set fixed line tariffs, (v) to allocate spectrum, (vi) in administering universal service. (vii) Budget independence. (viii) Term in office for regulators, (ix) Appointment rules; and (x) Dismissing powers. IRI is along the same lines as the indices of Edwards and Waverman (2006) and Gual and Trillas (2006).

³⁴ For example, Bolivia had one of the regulators that stayed in his position for longer time, “surviving” to three different country presidents. Peru had one of the most stable agencies in the sub-continent, with only two regulators in 10 years.

la parte baja de LPI1 y LPI2. Por el contrario, Jamaica tiene un lugar bajo en la independencia *de jure* pero un alta clasificación en la independencia combinada con *de facto*.

Table 4. Ranking IR1, LPI1 and LPI2. 1990-2004 average.

#	Country	IR1	Country	LPI1	Country	LPI2
1	Argentina	0.647	Peru	0.581	Peru	0.947
2	Bolivia	0.487	Bolivia	0.577	Jamaica	0.793
3	Panama	0.459	Argentina	0.490	Colombia	0.774
4	El Salvador	0.441	Brazil	0.478	Bolivia	0.710
5	Peru	0.428	Venezuela	0.468	Argentina	0.590
6	Brazil	0.422	Jamaica	0.460	Panama	0.563
7	Paraguay	0.416	Honduras	0.443	Venezuela	0.557
8	Chile	0.400	Mexico	0.415	Belice	0.550
9	Ecuador	0.387	Paraguay	0.408	Paraguay	0.508
10	Nicaragua	0.371	Colombia	0.385	Costa Rica	0.485
11	Costa Rica	0.370	Panama	0.380	Mexico	0.448
12	Venezuela	0.314	Belice	0.350	Brazil	0.411
13	Belice	0.300	Barbados	0.265	Nicaragua	0.385
14	Honduras	0.286	Ecuador	0.260	El Salvador	0.354
15	Colombia	0.281	Trinidad and T	0.240	Trinidad and T	0.340
16	Trinidad and T	0.279	Uruguay	0.227	Chile	0.333
17	Barbados	0.264	El Salvador	0.221	Barbados	0.299
18	Jamaica	0.253	Chile	0.200	Dominican R.	0.258
19	Dominican R.	0.249	Costa Rica	0.185	Uruguay	0.227
20	Mexico	0.229	Nicaragua	0.181	Guatemala	0.225
21	Uruguay	0.187	Dominican R.	0.125	Ecuador	0.193
22	Guatemala	0.183	Guatemala	0.091	Honduras	0.143
23	Surinam	0.047	Surinam	0.023	Surinam	0.023

Source: Montoya & Trillas (2007) and Author's calculations

4. Basic Econometrics

The purpose of this section is to use the index constructed in the previous section to perform similar exercises to those that have been carried out with legal indices of regulation, so that the performance of both types of indices can be compared. To analyze the impact of independence on telecommunications performance, the general model we use can be expressed as:

$$Y_{it} = B_1I_{it} + B_2X_{2it} + B_3X_{3it} + \dots X_{kit} + \mu_{it} \quad (1)$$

where $X_{it} = (X_{2it}, X_{3it}, \dots X_{kit})$ are the explanatory variables, including an independence index (IR1, LPI1 or LPI2) and control variables. $B = (B_1, B_2, \dots B_K)$ are their respective parameters and μ_{it} is an error term. We use individual fixed effects for the 23 countries.

The error term is modelled as:

$$\mu_{it} = \mu_i + v_{it} \quad (2)$$

where μ_i denotes non-observable individual effects and v_{it} denotes the remainder of the residual.

The performance dependent variable Y_{it} in equation (1) are fixed telephone lines for every 100 inhabitants, obtained from the International Telecommunications Union data base. The indices IR1, LPI1 and LPI2 are our main explanatory variable of interest.

Along the lines of other work in this field se espera que la expansión de la red se vea potencialmente afectada por la estructura económica y el desempeño sectorial. Para esto se incluyen las variables de control: para la estructura económica se usa el GDP purchasing power parity per capita (GDPppp) como medida bruta de su estructura económica y sus recursos. Como aproximación del desempeño sectorial se utiliza el Trade (exports plus imports as % of GDP). We obtained those variables from the data base of the World Bank. We expect that an increase in income per capita and trade are associated with higher demand for telephone services.³⁵

Table 6. Parameter Estimate for Main Lines per 100 Inhabitants.			
23 Countries. 1990-2004. Fixed effects			
Regressors	1	2	3
IR1	6.784*		
t	9.40		
LPI1		6.350*	
t		9.91	
LPI2			3.447*
t			7.63
GDPppp	0.003*	0.003*	0.003*
t	10.08	10.17	9.52
Trade	0.038***	0.045***	0.055***
t	1.34	1.60	1.86
Country dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes
R-sqr	0.77	0.78	0.80
N-obs.	345	345	345

Notes. * statistically significant at 1%. ** statistically significant at 5%. *** statistically significant at 10%.

³⁵ Gual and Trillas (2004 and 2006) find that the correlation between the equally weighed index and the one derived from principal components analysis is above 0.9. Based on this, in the rest of this study we use equally weighted indices, although recognising that there may be some residual multicollinearity between the original variables.

We estimate a Linear equation by OLS with fixed effects³⁶ Using IR1 (1), LPI1 (2) and LPI2 (3). For the 15 years and 23 countries of our sample, Table 6 shows that higher independence is associated with higher network expansion. In all equations the coefficient for independence is positive and with high values (3.45-6.78), and the *t* ratio is robust to heteroscedasticity³⁷. The results confirm those reported in most of previous studies³⁸.

Los datos confirman que la independencia bien medida tiene un impacto positivo y significativo (no sé si insistir en que el coeficiente de IR1 es el mayor)

GDP per capita and Trade are a positive and significant determinant of network expansion, but the magnitude of the effect is low: a one thousand dollar increase in income per capita is associated to a very small growth in the network. The results for those variables coincide with those obtained by Ros (1999 and 2003) and Gutierrez (2003), suggesting that the income elasticity of fixed telephony demand is quite low after some minimum threshold is achieved.

5. Conclusions

Telecommunications privatization was widespread in Latin America and the Caribbean in the 1990s. Coinciding with or immediately after privatization, regulatory agencies were created in many countries. Many of these agencies were given some degree of legal independence from government, to facilitate commitment not to expropriate sunk investments. One problem of course is that independence does not solve, but it relocates, the commitment problem, which transforms itself into one of the government credibly committing not to undermine the independence of the regulator, which many countries have found very difficult. Independence in practice improved over time, especially since 2000, but some countries' governments encountered serious problems in committing to preserve regulator independence.

This is the first study that measures independence in practice. We obtained detailed information about the practice of independence in 23 Latin American and Caribbean countries between 1990 and 2004, and constructed with this information two indices of independence that combines legal and practice issues, borrowing from the methodology used in the Central Bank Independence literature.

EVALUADOR TRES SUGUIERE: "the LPI index shed some lights about the efforts governments must do in order to provide stability to the regulatory environment and so this could also strengthen in the conclusions and recommendations."

³⁶ Wooldridge (2006) señala que cuando la unidad de observación es una unidad geográfica grande (cómo estados o naciones), no se pueden tratar a las muestras como muestras aleatorias de grandes poblaciones. Indica que los Efectos Fijos (EF) son adecuados para tratar con datos de panel ante muestras de países.

³⁷ We used year dummy variables without significant changes in the results.

³⁸ Like Gutierrez (2003a) and Ros (2003).

Estimation results confirm that regulator independence is associated to higher network penetration. This is based on purely illustrative econometric exercises. Our claim is not that this provides a rigorous quantification of the causal relationship between independence and investment. The main focus here is on the measurement of independence. We leave for future research a full investigation of the causal relationship, taking into account a better set of control variables as well as the potential endogeneity of policies and institutions, including the potential endogeneity of regulator independence.

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